

Planning and Prototyping Digital Twin for Educational Building

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Abstract

The thesis researches the planning and prototyping of a digital twin (DT) to improve energy efficiency and user comfort in an educational building. The chosen approach combines quantitative and qualitative methods and technical solutions of DT, which can also be used for educational purposes, with the aim of advancing BIM and DT technologies for the future.

The thesis provides a comprehensive literature review, the goals and objectives for the use of DT, supporting scenarios of use and applications of DT and investigation of indoor characteristics that can be measured by IoT (Internet of Things) sensors, which are available on the market and feasible for the selected project. In the DT planning phase, a sensor placement strategy was developed. It was based on historical data, collected data on energy consumption and occupancy patterns of spaces, and a survey using Dalux Environment to capture 360° photographs of the case study building. Following this, an economic evaluation of the proposed technical solutions was conducted. These steps led to the creation of a DT prototype adopted to the selected scenario, using Autodesk Tandem. In addition, the thesis outlines a systematic approach to the use of BIM and as-built modelling, which plays a crucial role in the development and implementation of building DTs.

This work is potentially interesting because of the in-depth research on DT and the process of implementing DT with BIM. The results can be used for research and educational purposes

and enable the inspection of the building, its operation and also the improvement of well-being.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/7k9MUnpxtbc>

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